

CDA NEWSLETTER

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CDA Celebrates 10th Year Anniversary, Unveils New Centre's Logo

ALSO INSIDE

CDA SIGNS AGREEMENT TO PRODUCE 100,000 DATEPALM SEEDLINGS TO JIGAWA STATE

MACARTHUR PRESIDENT, JOHN PALFREY VISITS CDA, IMPRESSED WITH SEX IDENTIFICATION OF DATEPALM SEEDLINGS

NUC ACCREDITATION TEAM EXCITED WITH CDA FARM, LABORATORIES

CDA
BAYERO UNIVERSITY
KANO

**CENTRE FOR
DRYLAND AGRICULTURE**
AN AFRICA CENTRE OF EXCELLENCE

CENTRE FOR DRYLAND AGRICULTURE

Bayero University, Kano – Nigeria

... an Africa Centre of Excellence

VISION

Resilient and Prosperous African Drylands

MISSION

To improve livelihood, resilience and sustainable use of natural resources in African drylands through training and demand-driven research

CORE VALUES

- Good leadership and Inclusiveness
- Passion and Teamwork
- Commitment and Sacrifice
- Integrity and Transparency
- Professionalism and Excellence

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The New CDA Logo being unveiled by the Deputy Governor, Kano State and Vice Chancellor, while Director CDA and DD Training assist

CDA Celebrates 10th Year Anniversary, Unveils New Centre's Logo

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) on Wednesday, 16th February, 2022 organized an Open Day to mark its 10th Year Anniversary. The event was chronicled by the unveiling of an iconic new logo of the Africa Centre of Excellence in dryland agriculture, which was performed by the Deputy Governor of Kano State, Dr. Nasiru Yusuf Gawuna, Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas and the Director of the Centre, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin.

The Centre also distributed seeds, seedlings and equipment to farmers from the adopted 22 communities and others.

Established in 2012 to serve as a regional training hub for the West and Central Africa (WCA) sub-region,

the CDA marked 10 years of incredible rise to stardom as one of the most competitive Africa Centres of Excellence with state-of-the-art facilities of international standard, competent and dedicated staffing, as well as vibrant research and training activities.

The Deputy Governor of Kano State, Dr. Nasiru Yusuf Gawuna, who was the Special Guest of Honour congratulated the CDA for achieving this milestone in just 10 years of existence, stating that Kano State Government was aware of the CDA's exceptional performance, which led to attracting another world bank grant of \$5m.

Dr Gawuna explained that the quality of research and training conducted in the CDA was of

international standard, noting that the Kano State Government would collaborate with the Centre to use some of its best researches to formulate policies or facilitate them to become laws that would address the deepening food security challenges.

The Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, in his remarks, said the day marked a landmark achievement in the annals of the University's history. He said CDA had made the University proud and "that's why we hold it in high esteem."

The Vice Chancellor reiterated that the University Management would continue to support the Centre to achieve its desired objectives. He congratulated the CDA, its staff and all the stakeholders for the giant strides recorded in 10 years.

Prof Abbas, who also represented the Executive Secretary of the National Universities Commission (NUC), Professor Abubakar Adamu Rasheed, said NUC was aware of the CDA's pre-eminent position among other Nigerian and African Centres of Excellence. He said the NUC would continue to support the Centre.

The quality of research and training conducted in the CDA are of international standard, Kano State Government will collaborate with the Centre to use some of its best researches to formulate policies or to facilitate them to become laws that will address the deepening food security challenges

From right: DVC Academic, Prof. Muhammad Sani Gumel, DVC Management Services, Prof. Mahmud Umar Sani, and the Registrar, Jamil Salim during the event

Director of CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin making welcome remarks

Program Manager, LINKS, Ms Roxanne Abdulali

Country Director of ICRISAT, Dr. Hakeem Ajiege

VC, Prof Sagir Abbas (right) presenting an award to Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin

Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin, in a discussion with Polaris Bank Executive Director, Abdullahi S. Mohammed

Polaris Bank Seeks Collaboration with CDA

The Management of Polaris Bank on Tuesday, 1st March, 2022 visited the Centre for Dryland Agriculture and expressed interest in collaborating with the Centre to develop the agricultural sector in Nigeria.

The management of the Bank, led by its Executive Director, Abdullahi S. Mohammed, said the Bank was

providing support for its international clients who were set to invest in the country on export commodities. According to him, the CDA would play a major role in supporting the Bank's platform in aggregating farmers, training on good agronomic practices and providing commodity quality assurance services.

The team was taken round to see the Centre's laboratories and Research and Training Farm. The Executive Director said with the state-of-the-art facilities at CDA, the Bank was optimistic in sealing a partnership with the Centre that would benefit both parties.

He said the Bank would also identify the areas to intervene in CDA as part of its corporate social responsibilities in tertiary institutions. The team also applauded the initiative of the CDA to build an innovation hub.

The Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, welcomed the team and assured that the CDA and University were ready for the collaboration as this would impact positively on the livelihood of Nigerians.

Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin (middle) in group a photograph with Polaris Bank delegation during the courtesy visit

CDA Signs Agreement to Produce 100,000 Datepalm Seedlings for Jigawa State

The Jigawa State government has signed an agreement with Bayero University, Kano (BUK) and the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) to produce 100,000 sex-identified Datepalm seedlings for distribution to farming communities across Jigawa State. The agreement, which was earlier endorsed by the Vice Chancellor, Professor Sagir Adamu Abbas, was signed in Dutse on Wednesday March 23, 2022 by the Honourable Commissioner for Agriculture during the opening ceremony of a Policy Workshop on indigenous tree restoration organized by the CDA.

The Commissioner for Agriculture, Muhammad Alhassan, who represented the Executive Governor, Alhaji Mohammed Badaru Abubakar (MON), was accompanied by the Commissioner for Land, the Managing Director of the Jigawa Agricultural and Rural Development Authority (JARDA) and several Permanent Secretaries and Directors from the State.

Datepalm is known to be dioecious, with separate male and female plants. During the establishment of plantations, it is difficult to identify the fruit bearing female plants at the seedling stage. To address this problem, scientists from Bayero University, Kano comprising Drs Suleiman Babura, Lawan Sani and Kabir Mustapha Umar developed a procedure for molecular sex identification at early growth state.

The sex-identified seedlings can then be micropropagated using tissue culture techniques. This will ensure the sustainable supply of quality seedlings and enable farmers to cultivate a sufficiently large number of productive female trees with a minimal number of male trees.

During the signing ceremony, the Jigawa State Commissioner for Agriculture stated that “we are signing this contract for the propagation of sex-identified datepalm for the benefit of our people, especially women”.

Jigawa State Governor, Alhaji Badaru Abubakar (right) appreciating the explanation made to him by Ibrahim Musa Maina (right), Head Crop Production of CDA Farm, while Director CDA, Prof Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin (2nd left) and Commissioner for Agriculture, Jigawa State (left) listen

The Director of the CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, noted that the Centre had developed a datepalm sex identification technique as a direct response to a request by the Association of Professional Farmers of Kano and Jigawa States, who came to CDA and complained about their losses in resources, labour and time spent on datepalm sometimes for more than five years before realizing the plants were male and would not bear fruits.

With this new technique and the tissue culture

facility at the CDA, the desired proportions of female and male seedlings can be propagated and distributed to farmers. According to him, Jigawa state felt within the region where datepalm could be cultivated at a commercial scale, adding that the state had conducive soil and climatic conditions for datepalm cultivation.

The existence of local varieties with good fruit qualities and strategic geographical location that enables double fruiting season shows the potential of the state in commercial date palm production.

Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin (left) and Commissioner for Agriculture, Jigawa State during the signing of MoU for CDA to produce 100,000 datepalm seedlings to the state

Deputy Director Research of CDA, Dr. Kabir Mustapha Umar (2nd left) briefing the Jigawa State Governor, Alh. Badaru Abubakar (2nd right) about the functions of Molecular Biology Laboratory, while Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin (left) and Commissioner for Agriculture, Jigawa State (2nd right) look on

Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin explaining the geographical map of CDA Research and Training Farm to the Jigawa State Governor, Alhaji Badaru Abubakar

Jigawa State Governor, Alhaji Badaru Abubakar (left) explaining a point at the CDA Lab to the Director CDA, while Dr. Kabir Mustapha Umar and Commissioner for Agriculture, Jigawa State (left) listen

A discussion on collaboration between CDA and Jigawa State Government at the Office of Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin (left) with the Governor, Alhaji Badaru Abubakar (middle) and Commissioner for Agriculture

MacArthur President, John Palfrey Visits CDA,

Impressed with Sex Identification of Datepalm Seedlings

The Mac Arthur President, Mr. John Palfrey on Tuesday, 22nd March, 2022 visited the Centre for Dryland Agriculture and was taken round to see the facilities of the Centre by the Director, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin.

The Mac Arthur President said he was particularly impressed with the Centre's new research of identifying the sex of datepalm.

While welcoming the President to the CDA Tissue Culture Laboratory, the Centre's Director told the President that date fruits were a highly valued delicacy among many communities in Nigeria and enjoyed a great spiritual and cultural significance. He said before the recent discovery by the CDA, farmers were finding it difficult to identify male from female seedlings until after about five years of planting before they would realize that most were males and could not bear fruits.

He further explained that the CDA was established through a competitively won take-off grant from MacArthur Foundation of \$800,000 and metamorphosed to become one of the Africa Centres of Excellence with advanced laboratory equipment of international standard.

Dr Lawan Sani explaining a point to the President of MacArthur, Mr John Palfrey (2nd right) and Vice Chancellor of BUK, Professor Sagir Abbas (left) at the CDA Tissue Culture Laboratory

MacArthur President, Mr John Palfrey and his team inspecting tissue cultured datepalm seeds at the CDA Tissue Culture Laboratory

MacArthur President, Mr John Palfrey and his team inspecting the hardening of tissue cultured datepalm in the CDA Nursery

Dr Sulaiman Babura (left) briefing the MacArthur President and his team about the hardening of tissue cultured datepalm

CDA Conducts Regional Training in Maradi on Statistical Analyses

The Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Bayero University, Kano organized a 6-day Regional Training Workshop on Data Collection and Statistical Analyses using the R-package for academic staff, researchers and partners of the Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University Maradi (UDDM).

The training, which, was targeted at staff, students and partners of the Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University Maradi (UDDM), was held from Monday 21st March to Saturday 26th March, 2022 at the Conference Hall of the Faculty of Agronomy and Environmental Sciences, UDDM.

The training objective was to strengthen the capacity of the participants in statistical analysis to further increase their ability, skills and knowledge while improving the quality of output and efficient performance.

The Deputy Vice Chancellor of the UDDM, Dr Adamou Saidou, who represented the Vice Chancellor during the opening ceremony, expressed appreciation to the CDA and by extension Bayero University, Kano for the bond of brotherhood, which the Centre has been displaying since its existence.

Training in session

A group photograph of participants during the training in Maradi

He urged the participants to utilize the rare opportunity towards ensuring that they make maximum use of the training towards better capacitating their skills and knowledge in statistical analyses.

The Acting Dean of the Faculty of Agronomy and Environmental Sciences of the Dan Dicko Dankoulodo University Maradi, Dr Elh Gounga Mahamadou, in his remark, applauded the strong ties between the CDA-BUK and UDDM since the establishment of the former; stressing that the CDA was one of the strong partners of the University. He thanked the Centre for the laudable efforts at strengthening

the capacity of its staff, students and partners.

In his remark, the Deputy Director (Training) of the CDA, Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed stated that over the years, the UDDM had prove to be a dependable partner of the Centre urging the University management to continue to support the faculty in its collaborations with the CDA.

A total of thirty-six participants comprising thirty-three (33) males and three (3) female trainees participated in the training. The training displayed high enthusiasm and zeal during the training sessions and expressed delight in participating in the training.

Another group photograph of participants after the training in Maradi

Deputy Governor, Kano State, Dr. Nasiru Yusuf Gawuna (right) and Vice Chancellor, Prof Sagir Adamu Abbas (left) observing the National Anthem

From Left. Prof E.U Essiet, Hajiya Karima Babangida, Prof Falola and Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin

Deputy Governor, Kano State, Vice Chancellor, BUK and other dignitaries standing for National Anthem

Staff and other participants listening to Program Manager, LINKS, Ms Roxanne Abdulali

Professor Sanusi Gaya Mohammed introducing some equipment to the Deputy Governor and other dignitaries

Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin (right), explaining one of CDA products to the Deputy Governor, Kano State, Dr Nasiru Gawuna (middle) and the Vice Chancellor, Prof. Sagir Adamu Abbas

Community leader and representative of CDA adopted communities expressing gratitude over seedlings given to them by CDA

Director CDA, Prof Jibrin M. Jibrin (left) and Prof. Sanusi Gaya Mohammed (with mic) explaining the function of stover crusher machine to the dignitaries

Communications Officer of CDA, Nura Garba and Malam Jazuli amidst other staff members during the event

Some of CDA Fresh From The Farm produce on display

Registrar of BUK being invited by Prof Amina Mustapha (2nd left) and assisted by Prof S.G Mohammed (2nd right) for award presentations

Mal. Ismail Nasir Usman receiving his award from the Registrar as the **Outstanding Cleaner/Messenger of CDA**

Mal. Sani Umar receiving his award from the Registrar as the **Outstanding Gardener of CDA**

Mal. Sagiru Umar receiving his award from the Registrar as the **Outstanding Driver of CDA**

Mal. Aliyu Zubairu receiving his award from the Registrar as the **Outstanding Admin Staff of CDA**

Registrar presenting an award to IMM as the **Outstanding CDA Farm Staff**, and being assisted by Prof Sanusi Gaya (middle)

An award for the **Outstanding CDA Technical (Laboratory) Staff** being presented and received on behalf of the recipient, Dayyabu Yahaya

Mal. Abubakar Mohammed Inuwa (left) receiving his award as the **Outstanding CDA Extension Agent**

Vice Chancellor, Prof Sagir Abbas, presenting an award plaque to Alhaji Ali Safiyanu Madugu, CEO Dala Foods

VC presenting a plaque to Chairperson WOFAN, Hajjiya Salamatu Garba

VC presenting a plaque to ICRIASAT Country Director, Dr Hakeem Ajeigbe

Hon. Mannir Babba Dan Agundi receiving his plaque from the Vice Chancellor for his immense support to CDA

Hajjiya Karima Babangida (Chairperson, SIAB) displaying an award presented to her by the Vice Chancellor

Prof E.U Essiet (left) receiving his award from the Vice Chancellor as one of pioneer Board members of the CDA

Prof Falola (left) receiving his award from the Vice Chancellor as one of pioneer Board members of the CDA

Deputy Governor, Kano State, Dr. Nasiru Yusuf Gawuna (right), presenting an award plaque to the Vice Chancellor, Prof Sagir Abbas for his support to CDA

CDA New logo about to be unveiled

Best Poster Presenter receiving his award from the Registrar, Malam Jamil Salim

Second best poster presenter receiving her award from the DVC Management Services, Prof Mahmud Umar Sani

Dr Halima Abdulkadir Idris receiving her prize for the third best poster presentation from DVC Academics, Prof M.S Gumel (right)

Deputy Director, Research of CDA, Dr Kabir Umar Mustapha offering the closing prayer

Group photograph of dignitaries, awardees and CDA staff

AFD Country Director Interacts with CDA, ACEPHAP

The Country Director of the French Development Agency (AFD), Mr. Xavier Muron has interacted with the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) and Africa Centre of Excellence for Population Health and Policy (ACEPHAP) at CDA's Conference Hall.

The interaction centred around the two centres' research areas, training, staffing, students, collaboration and partnership, as well as relationship with the industries. The aim was for the Country Director to understand the centres' status in terms of achievements, challenges and plans ahead.

The Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, while welcoming the Country Director, stressed on the evolution of the CDA which he said was established in 2012 with \$800,000 MacArthur Foundation grant and later won a competitive World Bank grant of close to \$7 million in 2014 as an Africa Centre of Excellence.

The Director highlighted the Centre's trajectory in winning \$1 million during the mid-term review in the ACE 1 project when the centre was rated high as one of the top performing in Africa and the

\$5 million grant for ACE Impact Project in 2018. Additionally, he told the AFD Country Director that the CDA was competitively selected to serve as one of the host universities in Africa to host the PASET program.

He explained that PASET was an initiative of the governments of Senegal and Rwanda before other African governments, World Bank, United States of America and South Korea joined. The aim is to train high level manpower within Africa in order to help to address the challenges of Africa by Africans.

On her part, the Director of ACEPHAP, Professor Hadiza Galadanci, explained that the centre was newly established, but at the moment it had students from 14 African countries.

She stated the ACEPHAP's internship programme, research and training activities, as well as other achievements recorded within the few years of the existence.

The AFD Country Director was impressed with the achievements recorded so far. He said that the research and training activities of the centres were of high standard.

Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin (left) stating the CDA's activities and recent achievements to the Country Director of French Development Agency (AFD), Mr Xavier Muron and his team while Centre Leader of ACEPHAP, Professor Hadiza Galadanci listen

Minister of Environment Visits CDA, Pledges Collaboration on Climate Smart Agriculture

The Minister of State for Environment, Sharon Ikeazor on Friday, 4th February, 2022 visited Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) in company of the Director General of the Nigeria Agency for Great Green Wall, Dr. Bukar Hassan.

The Minister of State for Environment, Sharon Ikeazor (middle), showing appreciation to the Vice Chancellor, BUK, Professor Sagir Abbas (left), on the souvenir to be presented to her by the Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin (right)

The Minister was taken round the CDA Molecular and Tissue Culture Laboratory by the Vice Chancellor, Prof. Sagir Adamu Abbas, the Director CDA, Prof. Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, Deputy Directors, CDA collaborating faculty members and other CDA staff.

Mrs Ikeazor was visibly impressed with the state-of-the-art facilities at CDA and stated that the Ministry was ready to collaborate with the Centre on climate smart agriculture and training.

She noted that CDA had a lot to offer to the Ministry in terms of capacity building, raising and mass propagation of datepalm, assuring that the Centre was the right institution to collaborate with.

The Vice Chancellor, Prof. Abbas, while welcoming the Minister said the University was happy to receive her and expressed readiness for any collaboration with the Ministry. He assured that there were many other avenues through which the University would collaborate with the Ministry.

In his remarks, the Director, CDA, Prof. Jibrin M. Jibrin, told the Minister that CDA was one of the Africa Centres of Excellence with students from 14 African countries and one of the three centres selected to host the PASET PhD programmes. He said PASET was a programme being sponsored by African governments to train high level manpower in order to address the continent's developmental challenges.

According to him, PASET chose the best Centres in Africa to host its programmes, which CDA was among, noting that the Centre was hosting a PhD programme on Climate Change. He added that it could collaborate with the Ministry in terms of manpower development and provision of laboratory facilities for analysis.

Speaking on the Tissue Culture Laboratory, the Deputy Director, Research, Dr. Kabir Mustapha Umar, said the laboratory had a lot of activities, including the mass propagation of plants and regenerating the fast disappearing species.

Minister of State for Environment, Sharon Ikeazor inspecting facilities at CDA Tissue Culture Laboratory

CDA is one of the Africa Centres of Excellence with students from 14 African countries and one of the three centres selected to host the PASET PhD programmes. PASET chose the best centres in Africa to host its programmes which CDA is among

Minister of State for Environment, Sharon Ikeazor receiving CDA Farm grapes harvested from the Director of CDA, Prof. Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin (middle) while the Vice Chancellor, Prof. Sagir Adamu Abbas (left) looks on

CDA Hosts 8th Monthly Industry Lecture On Sustainable Agriculture in Africa

Mr Aart Van den Bos presenting the 8th CDA Industry Talk, while the Director CDA and participants listen with rapt attention

An Entrepreneur from The Netherlands, Mr Aart Van den Bos, on Tuesday, 24th January, 2022 presented the Centre for Dryland agriculture's 8th Monthly Industry Talk with the theme: ***"Sustainable Agriculture in Africa, Innovation and Entrepreneurship"***.

Mr Bos highlighted Nigeria's potentials in which agriculture should be made to become a sustainable means of creating wealth and generating employment to the teeming population. He dwelled on regenerative agriculture, which he said was profitable to farmers and cited an example that regenerative corn fields generated nearly twice the profit of conventionally managed corn fields.

He argued that despite the huge potentials of agricultural export, Europe had remained a difficult

market for export because of different stringent measures and regulations. He advocated the need for people to look around and explore the possibilities of exploiting the market around and pursue their mission with all the sense of doggedness in order to meet their aspirations of financial sustainability in agriculture.

The Guest Lecturer, who is the Founder/owner of Verbos Business Development, The Netherlands shared the experiences of his company's strategic projects in South Africa, Mexico, Uganda, Kenya, Burundi and some other countries. He advised the students to work hard and initiate ideas and projects that could lead into profitable enterprises.

The Director Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA), Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, in his

remarks, said one of the key points of the lecture was how to treat the environment in a sustainable way and making money out of it. He commended the speaker for translating science into a money making venture.

Earlier in his remarks, the Co-ordinator of the CDA Monthly Industry Talk, Dr. Murtala M. Badamasi, said it was the tradition of the Centre to invite resource persons from industries monthly to talk to the students and faculty members as part of its effort to bridge the gap between academia and industry.

It is the tradition of the Centre to invite resource persons from industries monthly to talk to the students and faculty members as part of its effort to bridge the gap between the academia and industry

Mr Aart Van den Bos responding to questions made by the participants

Professor Amina Mustapha, the CDA Deputy Director Outreach and Publications, presenting vote of thanks

The participants listening to presentation of Mr Aart Van den Bos

NUC Accreditation Team Excited with CDA Farm, Laboratories

The National Universities Commission (NUC) Accreditation Team for the Faculty of Agriculture visited the Centre for Dryland Agriculture (CDA) and was visibly excited with the ultra-modern Research and Training Farm, Molecular and Tissue Culture laboratories, as well as Geographic Information System (GIS) laboratory on Monday, 17th January, 2022.

The leader of the team, Professor Abubakar Kundiri, was taken round the CDA facilities with his team members by the Director, CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin, along with the Dean, Faculty of Agriculture, Professor A. B. Mohammed, and other members of the faculty.

The team expressed appreciation and commendation over the gigantic strides of the CDA and stated that students had the best facilities to learn firsthand experience in order to become well trained.

The team members congratulated the University for establishing what they termed as a life time investment.

Professor A.E Ibe from the Federal University of Technology Owerri (FUTO) was highly moved by the farm's all-year-round production capacity of crops and vegetables, stating that the Centre could sustain itself beyond the Africa Centres of Excellence (ACE) funds.

Members of NUC Accreditation Team inspecting facilities at Screen House of CDA Research and Training Farm

Chairman of NUC Accreditation Team Panel tasting the grapes harvested from CDA Farm

Director CDA, Professor Jibrin Mohammed Jibrin explaining a point on banana production in CDA Farm to the NUC Accreditation Team

Students have the best facilities to learn first hand experience in order to become well trained

CDA's XRF Machine Analyzes over 50,000 Samples

XRF (X-ray fluorescence) is an analytical technique used to determine the elemental composition of materials directly with much of sample preparation, making it an excellent technology for qualitative and quantitative analysis of material composition. It has a wide variety of applications, ranging from material identification to quality control and risk assessment in agriculture, oil and gas, metal fabrication, automotive and aerospace, scrap and precious metal recycling, mining and

exploration, construction and environmental engineering.

The XRF at the CDA has been a one-stop service provider for a broad range of up to 71 elements from fluorine to uranium in one single measurement run. Over 50,000 samples have been analyzed in the CDA laboratory for the determination of soil nutrient elements, fertilizer composition, trace elements in geological samples and heavy metals in a wide variety of samples at affordable cost and in good time.

CDA's FRESH FROM THE FARM

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